

THE ROLE OF MILITARY TERMINOLOGY IN LINGUISTICS

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Abstract: This article is devoted to the question of the role of military terminology in linguistics, and the definition and description of the concept of military term is considered.

Key words: military term, terminological field, classification, definition, word, phrase.

There is some information about the beginning of the use of the concept of terminology in the field of linguistics, it was first used in 1786 by the German scientist S. Schütz, it appeared in the French language in the 18th century, and in the English language in 1801 [8; 210]. T. Shippan to the concept of terminology: "Terminology is a system of terms that forms the basis of the vocabulary in this science. The terms are distinguished by their uniformity, ambiguity and accuracy as a clear and solid lexical layer. Based on the conducted research, it is recommended to add to the opinion of T. Shippan that the term can have multiple meanings. In the studies of D.S. Lotte, S.A. Chapligina, S.I. Korshunova, T.L. Kandelaki, terminology is said to be a special aspect of linguistics, which deals with the study of certain laws related to the place of terms at the grammatical level and their use in the language [5;16]. Terminology in different languages forms the basis of research directions. In particular, the study of terms in Uzbek linguistics began with the study of cotton terms, but now it is possible to witness the fact that the development and improvement of science and technology, as well as the development and improvement of economic production are also reflected in terminology to a certain extent.

Today's research on terminology is being carried out not only because of the interest in the nature and essence of terms, but also because the study of terms is a requirement and necessity of every field. The development of the science of terminology is considered to be closely related to the development of the entire society and state [1;23]. Due to the fact that the emergence of terms due to various technical inventions and developments in the language is considered a continuous process, this field is not only the main object of the science of terminology, but also another science.

According to Leuchik, the formation of terms is carried out on the basis of professional knowledge of each field, and the concepts they represent are

interpreted through terms. Accordingly, the linguistic status of military terms is formed under the influence of the field of military knowledge, at the same time, on the basis of linguistic and extralinguistic factors [3;256].

As one of the special terminologies, military terminology has a scientific basis and a definite meaning, together with the formed system of military terms existing in the language and the fact that each of them has a clear scope of application. The military term is a part of the language terminology system and has signs common to all terms. A military term is a word or combination of words that represents military work or armed forces, military equipment, and similar related concepts. In addition to the general requirements for military terms, the following features are characteristic of military terms: most military terms have two or more components (ballistic missile), the frequent use of abbreviations, the presence of eponyms (Kalashnikov assault rifle) [4;9].

The military lexicon is a special layer of the vocabulary of a certain language, and it is significant because it has a number of features compared to the general vocabulary. Knowing them makes it easier to understand the meaning of texts with a special, that is, military content. Military terminology includes many terms related to other fields of general engineering, science and technology, which are widely used in military work, as well as related military terms.

The military vocabulary of a given language reflects various military concepts and is a lexical unit used in a special communication process. N.V. Shevchuk calls concepts related to forms and methods of war, issues of strategic use of armed forces, weapons and technical equipment as military terms. Based on the above, it can be said that military terms are actively used in oral and written speech of a military content as a language unit that reflects a specific specific meaning.

When it comes to military terminology, it is appropriate to first answer the question of what a military term is. A military term is a term whose content is related to the subject of military work, characterized by nominativeness, lack of expressiveness and ambiguity, consistent with modern knowledge, in some cases in several languages. is a word or phrase that has the same meaning [2;11]. V.N. Shevchuk defines military terminology as "an organized collection of military terms in the language" and the use of armed forces for strategic purposes, as well as their organization, arming and equipping of military departments, units and units, operational-tactical use, and related to them. It is defined as words and phrases that express concepts such as forms and methods

of fighting [12;488].They said that it is manifested in the form of a synthetic or analytical stable unit strengthened by a certain concept in the conceptual-functional system of a certain military profession. According to the definition mentioned above, military terms are a collection of words and phrases that incorporate knowledge related to various fields of military knowledge.

Due to the wide field of military activity, terms related to various knowledge, such as tactical, military technical, armed forces, are included in the specific terminological layer of the military language. Each of them has its own terminological field. Accordingly, Yu.N. Sdobnova suggests dividing military terminology into the following different groups: military units of the armed forces, military equipment, personnel, military-political, command-line, military topographical terms [11; 195-209].

Military terms have systematic, nominative, unequivocal and stylistically neutral features in their terminological field. It is recognized by Pirikov [9; 98-111]. In addition to the above classification, Ye.D. Isayeva says that the terms military orders, operational tactics, military management, and military engineering also belong to the group of military terminology. Of course, it is considered necessary to include the concepts of all processes related to military work in the military terminology. Yu.O. Lukyanchuk also expressed his views on terms of the military sphere, emphasizing that military terms include words and phrases related to ground forces, air forces, military communications, and engineering troops[7; 65-67]. He givesIn general, the military field is unique due to the fact that it is very broad in terms of coverage, and for this reason, every scientist expressed his views on the issue.

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